

DGIP-CEDS

Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance
in Common European Data Spaces

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Data Management Plan (D6.1)

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1 Introduction: project summary

The development of a data-driven economy that capitalises on the potentials of digital transformation could bring huge benefits across sectors and domains (such as the provision of more personalised healthcare, improved energy efficiency or more efficient transport systems), but it also poses significant risks and challenges (including the necessity to mitigate/eliminate risks and balance often competing rights and interests associated with data usage). To maximise those potentials, in its European Strategy for Data (2020), the Commission set forth to create a single market for data by setting rules on access to, sharing of and reuse of data, supplemented by the development of Common European Data Spaces in a broad range of sectors and domains. In support of those efforts, during the 2019–24 political mandate, the EU adopted several horizontal legislative acts (Data Governance Act, Data Act, AI Act), as well as the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation, the first sectoral legislative framework for a Common European Data Space. However, certain aspects of those legislative acts have been criticised by stakeholders for failing to ensure legal consistency, fair allocation of rights and responsibilities and due mitigation/elimination of data protection and intellectual property (IP)-related risks.

Acknowledging the pressing challenges ahead of its 2024–2029 mandate, the European Commission has pledged to draw on existing data rules to ensure a simplified, clear and coherent legal framework for data sharing at scale under the (forthcoming) European Data Union Strategy. At the same time, as numerous EU-funded data space pilot projects are making strides, discussions on the creation of Common European Data Spaces are expected to enter a more advanced (possibly legislative) stage in further sectors and domains. In anticipation of those developments, the ‘Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance in Common European Data Spaces’ (DGIP-CEDS) project analyses how existing and future legislative frameworks (and accompanying contractual frameworks) could be fine-tuned or conceptualised to ensure the adoption and implementation of fair data economy principles in Common European Data Spaces. DGIP-CEDS intends to contribute to EU policy developments by identifying cross-sector commonalities and developing, where possible, common or similar data governance and related IP governance solutions, which could be adopted or implemented across different sectors or domains. As Common European Data Spaces are being developed in sectoral or domain-specific silos, DGIP-CEDS seeks to aggregate and transmit knowledge between the development of data spaces to support the adoption of adequate, effective and consistent legal frameworks.

2 Data management: guiding principles

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the data management policy of the DGIP-CEDS project. The DMP provides descriptions of the relevant datasets and defines the purposes as well as the technical and organisational measures regarding how data concerning research, project management, and contact and administration issues are managed and processed (collected/generated, organised, analysed, shared, stored, archived etc.) during the project and after the end of the project. The DMP is intended to guide project activities through various aspects of data management and related project documentation and publication activities. As part of this, the DMP includes descriptions of how the so-called 'FAIR' principles (i.e. findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable data) must be implemented in the data management practices of the project. The DMP also specifies which research outcomes shall be made publicly available (in line with the 'Open Access' policy), and which sensitive or confidential data should remain at the disposal of the data holder (restricted).

The data management practices of DGIP-CEDS are performed especially with consideration to the legislative acts and Commission work programmes establishing and governing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation ⁽¹⁾, as well as the applicable provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation) ⁽²⁾ and the Croatian Copyright and Related Rights Act (no. 111/2021) ⁽³⁾. The DMP is formulated in line with the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan template ⁽⁴⁾ published by the European Commission, and is with respect to the applicable provisions of Grant agreement no.: 101210413 — DGIP-CEDS. The DMP guides the data management activities of the beneficiary (coordinating entity) within the scope of the project.

This DMP deliverable (6.1) is prepared at the outset of the project, but is intended to function as a 'living' document, which will undergo a comprehensive review at the start of the second year of the project (M13) in the form of another deliverable (6.3), if any updates are deemed necessary to the present document. The (present and updated) DMP will also support the compliance assessment of all project activities at the end of the project (M24).

¹ European Commission, *EU Funding & Tenders Portal* (Reference documents: 2021–2027, Horizon Europe [HORIZON]), <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON?programmePeriod=2021-2027&frameworkProgramme=43108390>.

² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1–88, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.

³ Croatian Parliament, Law on Copyright and Related Rights, NN 111/2021, 6.10.2021, <https://narodne-novine.nn.hr/eli/sluzbeni/2021/111/1941>.

⁴ European Commission, *Horizon Europe Data Management Plan*, EU Grants: Data management plan (HE):V1.1 – 01.04.2022, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx.

3 Data management: key issues

3.1 Data summary

3.1.1 Re-use of existing data and its origins

The relevant deliverables (reports, scientific papers, conference presentations, university presentations) of the DGIP-CEDS project will build on existing knowledge through literature review and desk research outcomes. In principle, the collection of existing data will be based on the application of the so-called Boolean search logic (i.e. the search of relevant terms with regard to the logical relationships between them) with the support of open source AI assistant search tools.

When re-using data, DGIP-CEDS will make references or give appropriate credit to the following sources of existing data:

- legislation, judicial interpretations and other authoritative guidances (e.g. case-law, guidelines, recommendations, model contractual terms and standard contractual clauses, standards);
- publications (books/monographs, articles in scientific journals and conference proceedings, commentaries, studies and white papers, websites) by EU bodies, Member State authorities, standardisation bodies, EU-funded projects, stakeholders and/or scholars;
- publicly available recordings, transcripts and slides of presentations, webinars, and conference keynotes and panels.

3.1.2 Types of data collected/generated and its purposes and relation to the research objectives

3.1.2.1 Research data

DGIP-CEDS will collect/generate the following types of research data:

- transcripts (based on voice recordings) of semi-structured interviews with experts and stakeholders involved in or directly affected by the development, deployment and/or implementation of Common European Data Spaces or other data spaces at the European and/or national level;
- photographs and/or summary notes from meetings or group discussions at self-organised events (e.g. workshop, roundtable, conference);
- qualitative analyses (including: structuring, application of logical connections, presentation) of existing re-used data and/or newly collected/generated research data;
- correspondence with relevant parties (e.g. email exchanges).

In terms of its form, research data may encompass: raw data (initially collected/generated data), cleaned data (data prepared for data analysis), processed data (data derived data analysis) and presentation data (data adapted for public presentation).

The purpose of processing the abovementioned research data sets is to undertake scientific research activities on data governance and intellectual property (IP) governance issues in Common European Data Spaces in order to produce new, original research results. When this entails the collection/generation of personal data, it is subject to the prior informed consent of data subjects, which may be obtained pursuant to the 'Annex: Research participation and data processing consent forms' of this DMP.

The planned research outcomes (main deliverables) of these activities are the following documents:

- Typology of data governance and IP governance in Common European Data Spaces (D1.1);
- Impact analysis of data governance and IP governance in the implementation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) (D2.1);

- Legal solutions to support the conceptualisation of data governance and IP governance requirements in Common European Data Spaces (D3.1);
- Scientific paper and conference presentation on fair data economy principles in Common European Data Spaces (D5.2);
- Scientific paper and conference presentation(s) on intellectual property (IP) governance in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation (D5.5);
- Conference presentation(s) on conceptualising data governance and IP governance requirements in future Common European data spaces (D5.6).

The relevant deliverables (reports, scientific papers, conference presentations, university presentations) may only include opinions/recommendations by data subjects (if it is based on new raw data) in so far as and in the manner that they explicitly approve the respective content. It is subject to prior approval by the data subject (pursuant to an email confirmation) and is a separate and subsequent step to the consent given prior to interviews or event participation pursuant to the 'Annex: Research participation and data processing consent forms' of this DMP.

Regarding data utility objectives, the collection/generation of research data by DGIP-CEDS aims to contribute to the development of Common European Data Spaces with a (suppletory) legal focus by helping to aggregate and transmit knowledge between data space developments that are taking place in silos. The collection of feedback from experts and stakeholders, including the identification of relevant needs and challenges, could help to design and implement more fitting and effective EU policy instruments concerning how data and IP rights should be regulated and governed in the European data economy of the future.

3.1.2.2 Project management data

DGIP-CEDS will collect/generate the following types of project management data:

- data on project finances;
- data on project activities and reporting.

The purpose of processing the abovementioned personal and non-personal project management data sets is to comply with Grant Agreement no.: 101210413 — DGIP-CEDS and related applicable legal obligations under EU and Croatian laws.

3.1.2.3 Contact and administrative data

DGIP-CEDS will collect/generate the following types of contact and administrative data:

- contact information (name, affiliation, email address) of participants of self-organised events;
- signed 'Research participation and data processing consent forms' (in Annex).

The processing of the abovementioned contact and administrative data sets is subject to the prior informed consent of data subjects, which is obtained with the use of the 'Annex: Research participation and data processing consent forms' of this DMP. The purpose is linked with the objective of collecting/generating research data to undertake scientific research activities concerning data governance and intellectual property (IP) governance issues in Common European Data Spaces.

3.1.3 Formats and expected size of data collected/generated

Data collected/generated or re-used by DGIP-CEDS will include: physical data (e.g. written notes from self-organised events) and digital data (e.g. digital texts, spreadsheets, slides, emails or photographs). Physical data will undergo digitisation, followed by the erasure of the original physical data. Any voice recordings of interviews will be converted from speech to text with the use of a state-of-the-art software.

By default, for the purpose of the objectives of DGIP-CEDS, anonymous data will be collected/generated. When personal data will be collected/generated for the necessary purposes defined in the preceding sub-

chapter or upon the consent of data subjects, processing will be performed in compliance with the data protection principles defined under Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation). To implement the principles of data minimisation, integrity and confidentiality, personal data will undergo pseudonymisation whenever it is adequate and relevant in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. Special categories of personal data and data which may reveal trade secrets will not be processed.

The overall size of data collected/generated in the project is estimated to reach around 5 GB.

3.2 'FAIR' (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data

The FAIR principles are a set of guidelines designed to improve the management and stewardship of research data, ensuring that data can be easily found, accessed, interoperated and reused by both humans and machines.⁽⁵⁾ The FAIR principles are widely recognised and aim to collectively ensure that data is discoverable, accessible under clear conditions, interoperable across systems and reusable for future research, thereby promoting openness, collaboration and transparency in science, and maximising the potential value of research data.

3.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data collected/generated within the DGIP-CEDS project will be organised in digital folders. Deliverable documents, task documents and related data sets will be organised by work packages. The project will ensure that deliverable documents, task documents and other data sets are uniquely identifiable and associated with a unique file name to ensure version control. Files will be named according to a standardised scheme (e.g. "DGIP_CEDS_D61_Data_management_plan_v01draft") to facilitate their findability and tracking. Document versions will be marked with serial numbers (v01draft, v02draft, v1final, v2final) to record modifications and any updates. Deliverable documents will include a table tracking key changes on drafting, review and finalisation (as relevant).

Metadata of deliverable documents will include data on the project name/acronym (DGIP-CEDS), name of the action (HORIZON TMA MSCA), grant agreement number (101210413), number of the work package and deliverable document, names of the author (MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow) and Project Coordinator, availability/accessibility (open/public, restricted), publication date, as well as a DOI (digital object identifier) link. To enhance the discoverability and potential re-use of deliverable documents, metadata will include specific keywords (e.g. Common European Data Spaces, legal, data governance, IP governance). Deliverable documents will also include a URL link to the English version of the project website (<https://pravri.uniri.hr/en/project/dgip-ceds/>), a sub-section of the coordinating entity's website. In turn, the project website will include links to the DOIs of published deliverable documents.

3.2.2 Making data openly accessible

The DGIP-CEDS project will apply the 'Open science' approach based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge as early and widely as possible in the process. Open/public deliverable documents will be published on the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>) and all deliverables will be deposited in the Zenodo EU Open Research Repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eu/>) under their respective terms and conditions. The ORE platform is an open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from EU-funded projects across all subject areas. It offers researchers a publishing venue to share research findings rapidly and facilitate open, constructive research discussion under a continuous publication schedule. The EU Open Research Repository serves as a complementary platform to the ORE publishing platform. It is managed by CERN on behalf of the European Commission and provides a space for all other research outputs (e.g. data sets, certain deliverables) that are out of scope for ORE. This holistic approach enables the project to

⁵ GO FAIR Initiative, *FAIR Principles*, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

not only publish the research results, but also to archive and under certain legal conditions share data and materials that support the findings, fostering transparency and reproducibility in the scientific process.

While it is envisaged that most deliverables will be open access and widely disseminated, access to certain deliverables (e.g. Career Development Plan [D4.1], Risk Management Plan [D6.2]) of the project will be protected under a restricted access regime available only to the author (MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow), the Project Coordinator, the Project and International Cooperation Office of the coordinating entity, the legal representative of the coordinating entity and the granting authority (upon request), in accordance with Grant Agreement no.: 101210413 — DGIP-CEDS.

3.2.3 Making data interoperable

Digital data collected/generated by the DGIP-CEDS project will be kept in commonly used, machine-readable and interoperable formats. Depending on their type and format, files may have the following extensions: .doc/.docx, .txt, .ppt/.pptx, .csv, .xls/.xlsx, .jpg, .png, .html, .zip, or .pdf.

In order to enrich the contextual knowledge about specific data, the project aims to integrate vast number of links between (meta)data resources through qualified references to other existing data.

3.2.4 Increasing data reuse, including management of IP rights

In accordance with Grant Agreement no.: 101210413 — DGIP-CEDS, the DGIP-CEDS project aims to disseminate research results as soon as feasible and “as open as possible as closed as necessary”, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of personal data, privacy, IP rights, trade secrets or other legitimate interests. The Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.1) sets the objectives and deadlines for communication and dissemination, identifying different target groups, specific measures and channels to reach them, as well as quantitative indicators to measure progress.

Publications (main deliverables, scientific papers and conference presentations) from the DGIP-CEDS project will be made available under the Diamond Open Access (OA) model and the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which means that reuse is allowed provided appropriate credit is given (in the form of any of the widely used citation styles), and any changes are indicated. For any use or reproduction of material that is not owned by the author (MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow) or the coordinating entity, permission must be sought directly from the copyright holder.

3.3 Data management roles, responsibilities and resources

The data management processes of the DGIP-CEDS project are performed and overseen by the participants of the project (who are all affiliated with the coordinating entity): the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (researcher), the Project Coordinator and the Project and International Cooperation Office of the coordinating entity. Adherence to the Open science principle is supported by the Head of the Library and European Documentation Centre of the coordinating entity.

The controller of personal data processing operations is the coordinating entity (University of Rijeka, Faculty of Law). Data subjects may exercise their rights relating to personal data processing by contacting the researcher or the Project Coordinator via email (see contact information on the inner cover page) or by writing to the coordinating entity (University of Rijeka, Faculty of Law, Hahlić 6, 51000 Rijeka, Croatia). Interested parties may also turn to the Data Protection Officer of the University of Rijeka (gdpr@uniri.hr).

No additional costs are foreseen for data collection/generation and for adhering to the FAIR principles. The use of the Open Research Europe platform and the Zenodo EU Open Research Repository do not entail additional costs for EU-funded research projects.

3.4 Data storage, information security and data retention/archiving

Draft versions of deliverables, other research data, project management data, as well as contact and administrative data are stored in the Microsoft OneDrive personal cloud storage spaces of the participants of the project. As raw data represents the foundation for further data analyses, such data sets are stored

in a separate and protected location from the working versions of the research data. Project management documents and the final version of deliverables (both open/public and restricted documents) will be uploaded to the 'DGIP-CEDS Group' Microsoft SharePoint folder accessible to the participants of the project and archived in the Zenodo EU Open Research Repository to ensure long-term preservation of research results. Restricted data storage spaces may be accessed by the participants of the project through the use of appropriate institutional authentication and login security tools.

The processing of personal data is limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed with respect to the principle of 'data minimisation'. Voice recordings made during interviews with experts and stakeholders will be deleted at the end of the project. The records and confidentiality of project management data are maintained by the coordinating entity in accordance with the time-limits set forth by the Grant Agreement no.: 101210413 — DGIP-CEDS.

3.5 Ethical aspects

The DGIP-CEDS project aims to adhere to the good research practices outlined in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity ⁽⁶⁾ and the principles on research ethics set forth in the University of Rijeka Code of Ethics ⁽⁷⁾.

⁶ ALLEA (European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities), *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*, Revised edition, 2023, <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>.

⁷ University of Rijeka Senate, *University of Rijeka Code of Ethics*, 17 July 2018, https://uniri.hr/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/UNIRI-Code-of-Ethics_2018.pdf.

Annex: Research participation and data processing consent forms (DGIP-CEDS project)

These Research participation and data processing consent forms constitute the Annex to the Data Management Plan of the “Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance in Common European Data Spaces (DGIP-CEDS)” project, which outlines the data management policy of the project. The full Data Management Plan is available on the project website (<https://pravri.uniri.hr/en/project/dgip-ceds/>) and deposited in the Zenodo EU Open Research Repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16811657>).

Information on the purpose of the data processing

The DGIP-CEDS project intends to contribute to EU policy developments by identifying cross-sector commonalities and developing, where possible, common or similar data governance and related IP governance solutions, which could be adopted or implemented across different sectors or domains. The collection/generation of research data within the DGIP-CEDS project aims to contribute to the development of Common European Data Spaces with a (supplementary) legal focus by helping to aggregate and transmit knowledge between data space developments that are taking place in silos. The DGIP-CEDS project conducts semi-structured interviews and organises dedicated events (workshop, roundtable, conference) with experts and stakeholders involved in or directly affected by the development, deployment and/or implementation of Common European Data Spaces or other data spaces at the European and/or national level. The collection of feedback (opinions, recommendations) from experts and stakeholders, including the identification of relevant needs and challenges, intends to help design and implement more fitting and effective EU policy instruments regarding how data and IP rights should be regulated and governed in the European data economy of the future.

Project information

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Project duration: 2025.04.01. – 2027.03.30.

Project website: <https://pravri.uniri.hr/en/project/dgip-ceds/>

Contacts

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Project coordinator: Prof. Dr. Sc. Ivana Kunda (ivana.kunda@uniri.hr)

Consent to research participation

I confirm that I have been informed about the purpose of the DGIP-CEDS project and I understand that my participation is voluntary:

- as an event (e.g. workshop, roundtable, conference) participant, or
- as an interviewee.

I may choose not to answer any questions and may withdraw from participation at any time without penalty.

Participant name: _____

E-mail address: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

The consent can be submitted either on paper or by e-mail.

Consent to data processing

I consent to the following data processing when I participate in:

- an event (e.g. workshop, roundtable, conference) organised within the DGIP-CEDS project:
 - photographs and summary notes from the event may be published on the DGIP-CEDS's project website and archived in a trusted repository (EU Open Research Repository);
 - my personal contribution (e.g. direct quote, slides) may be added to a project deliverable, subject to my prior confirmation (by e-mail) of the exact content, for publication on the Open Research Europe platform, the DGIP-CEDS's project website and/or a recognised scientific journal, and archived in a trusted repository (EU Open Research Repository);
- an interview with the researcher undertaking the DGIP-CEDS project:
 - to be asked questions regarding my expertise on data governance and/or IP governance issues relating to the development, deployment or implementation of Common European Data Spaces or related initiatives in the specific sector or domain that I am familiar with in the form of a semi-structured interview, which is expected to last cc. 40 minutes, and that my responses may be recorded by the researcher using voice recording technology based on which the transcript will be made, which will be archived in a trusted repository (EU Open Research Repository) and not made accessible to anybody outside the project, while the voice recording will be deleted at the end of the project;
 - my personal views or the views of the organisation that I represent may be transformed into a case study or direct quotes, which may be published as part of the dissemination of the DGIP-CEDS project with the agreed content, subject to my prior confirmation (by email), on the Open Research Europe platform, the DGIP-CEDS's project website and/or a recognised scientific journal, and archived in a trusted repository (EU Open Research Repository).

Data security:

I understand that the controller (University of Rijeka, Faculty of Law) implements appropriate technical and organisational measures to safeguard my personal data, as set out in the Data Management Plan. Special categories of personal data and data which may reveal trade secrets will not be processed and personal data will undergo pseudonymisation or anonymisation whenever it is adequate and relevant in relation to the purposes for which they are processed.

Rights as a data subject:

I understand that I may exercise my rights as a data subject in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation) by contacting the researcher or the project coordinator (in their capacity as controller) via email or by writing to the coordinating entity (University of Rijeka, Faculty of Law, Hahlić 6, 51000 Rijeka, Croatia). Interested parties may also turn to the Data Protection Officer of the University of Rijeka (gdpr@uniri.hr).

I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided above. I consent to the processing of my personal data within the DGIP-CEDS project as described.

Participant name: _____

E-mail address: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

The consent can be submitted either on paper or by e-mail.

**Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance
in Common European Data Spaces (DGIP-CEDS)**

[DGIP-CEDS project website](#)

University of Rijeka, Faculty of Law (PRAVRI)